

Comparative Analysis of Homelessness Monitoring in Europe for the 2030 Agenda

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Abstract: This paper explores homelessness in the EU, focusing on how different countries monitor the issue, particularly the existence and local implementation of monitoring frameworks. The 8th Overview of Housing Exclusion in Europe reports that at least 895,000 people across the EU are experiencing homelessness, either sleeping rough or in temporary accommodations - a 70% increase over the past decade. In response, the Lisbon Declaration on Combating Homelessness was signed by EU Member States, institutions, and civil society organizations, aiming to eradicate homelessness by 2030. The study's methodology includes desk research and interviews with experts in statistics and homelessness. Our findings show that EU member states have diverse legal definitions, national strategies, and local monitoring programs for homelessness. Additionally, the socio-demographic profiles of people experiencing homelessness vary significantly across countries.

JEL classification: R20; I30

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1 Introduction

Homelessness and housing exclusion are widespread and persistent in most European Union (EU) countries. According to estimates by FEANTSA (2023) in their 8th Overview of Housing Exclusion in Europe, at least 895,000 people in the EU are experiencing homelessness, either sleeping rough or in emergency or temporary accommodation on any given night – a rise of over 70% compared to a decade ago. Several EU Member States, including France, Germany, the Netherlands and Portugal, have seen an increase in homelessness rates as a share of their total population in recent years. By contrast, countries such as Austria, Denmark, Finland, Poland, Slovenia and Sweden have recorded either stable or declining rates. Broadly, the trend in homelessness is rising across Europe with Finland and Norway being notable exceptions. Additionally, the profile of those experiencing homelessness has shifted, increasingly encompassing young people and children, migrants, Roma, and other vulnerable groups (European Commission, 2014; OECD, 2021b; Sullivan et al., 2023).

In response to the growing number of people experiencing homelessness, efforts to combat homelessness have intensified. On June 21, 2021, EU Member States (MS), the European Parliament (EP), the European Commission (EC), EU Consultative bodies – the European Economic and Social Committee and the European Committee of the Regions - and EU-level networks of civil society organisations and social partners signed the Lisbon Declaration on Combating Homelessness. The signatories committed to ending homelessness in the EU by 2030, aligning with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) framework's "Leave No One Behind" principle.

To support and strengthen collaboration among of all stakeholders in achieving this goal - and to implement Principle 19 of the Pillar of Social Rights, which addresses housing and assistance for people experiencing homelessness – the Declaration's signatories have launched several initiatives, including the European Platform on Combatting Homelessness. This platform is designed to help Member States, cities, and service providers share best practices and identify effective and innovative approaches.

Also, national governments have implemented various policies in different areas to reduce homelessness. Some have adopted national strategies where the responsibility for serving people experiencing homelessness often falls under standard social welfare policies. Local authorities' Welfare departments make arrangements for residential accommodation and complementary services. In some cases, local authorities are also tasked with providing regular counts to the government.

Official estimates of the scale and distribution of homelessness are essential for evaluating policy effectiveness. For instance, Finland, alongside Norway, has been a pioneering country in Europe by adopting a national strategy based on the Housing First approach, which provides

individuals experiencing homelessness with immediate, independent, permanent housing rather than temporary accommodations (OECD, 2020). Finland was also the first Nordic country to collect nationwide data on homelessness in 1987. From then on, municipalities gather information on homelessness from various sources, including housing officials and municipal rental housing companies, social services, and service providers (Benjaminsen et al., 2020). Denmark, France and Ireland followed Finland in adopting Housing First-oriented policies and practices in 2008, 2010 and 2011, respectively (Baptista and Marlier, 2019). Spain has also developed a plan to combat homelessness, guided by principles of person-centred care, respect for self-determination, and individualized life projects (FEANTSA, 2022).

This paper provides an overview of how countries monitor homelessness in the EU and if this monitoring has a local dimension. We investigate the existence of a homelessness framework, legal definition, and monitoring level in each EU country, focusing on local monitoring. For instance, local governments are the closest to citizens and are those providing services for their communities, including individuals experiencing homelessness. The goal of the paper is to determine the methodology, disaggregation, operational definition of homelessness, and frequency of data collection in order to answer the following research question:

- How is the data on homelessness collected at the EU MS and local level, and what is the methodology used by different EU MS?
- What strategies have been implemented in different EU MS to reduce homelessness?

The first research question investigates how data on homelessness is collected at both the EU MS and local levels, as well as the methodologies employed by different EU MS. By examining the data collection processes, this paper aims to identify common practices, and variations in methodologies used across countries.

The second, by examining the strategies in place seeks to identify the various approaches taken by different countries to address homelessness and understand the diversity of strategies employed.

By addressing these research questions, this paper aims to provide a step forward in the understanding of homelessness data collection methodologies and strategies in European countries. The underlying idea is that monitoring produces power knowledge: monitoring is essential for public policymaking, and not tackling homelessness implies high social costs for those involved, for the society as a whole and for social cohesion. For individuals, the distress of lacking stable housing can lead to or worsen social isolation, create barriers to education, training, and employment and negatively impact both mental and physical health. Prolonged or repeated experiences of homelessness further erode health and well-being. To effectively support and provide services to those experiencing

homelessness, the first step is to closely monitor and thoroughly understand this issue.

The empirical strategy used to investigate the research question combines desk research with contacts and interviews with national statistical experts and experts on homelessness. The former explores the phenomenon from documents and previous research; the latter allows us to get additional information. The findings of this research will contribute to the existing knowledge on homelessness and inform future policy development and decision-making processes in the EU MS.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 briefly reviews the related literature about homelessness in EU countries; Section 3 presents definitions, and data collection methods and related efforts in the field of monitoring homelessness in Europe; Section 4 develops the methodology of this paper to integrate the existing knowledge on homelessness monitoring with a local perspective; Section 6 presents the results of the research in descriptive and figurative format, while Section 5 discusses conclusions and proposes recommendations for future research and policy uptake.

2 Literature Review

Research on homelessness in Europe has significantly expanded in recent decades, with scholars emphasizing the importance of robust monitoring systems to guide evidence-based policies. A central theme in the academic literature is the variability of definitions and data collection methodologies across countries, which complicates cross-national comparisons (Sullivan, 2023). The lack of a universally accepted definition, as noted by Casey and Stazen (2021), remains a core obstacle to integrating homelessness into global development agendas such as the SDGs.

One of the most widely discussed frameworks in European homelessness research is the European Typology of Homelessness and Housing Exclusion (ETHOS), developed by FEANTSA. ETHOS provides a multidimensional approach to defining homelessness, emphasizing physical, social, and legal aspects of “home”. ETHOS Light a streamlined version for statistical purposes, is recommended by UNECE and Eurostat (2006) and has informed census guidelines across the EU (Eurostat, 2019).

Despite ETHOS’s adoption, countries vary considerably in how they implement homelessness monitoring. Pleace and Hermans (2020) argue for ending separate enumeration of hidden homelessness to capture the full spectrum of housing exclusion. Their work, along with that of Bretherton and Mayock (2021), highlights the underrepresentation of vulnerable groups – especially women, youth, and LGBTQI+ populations – due to methodological biases in data collection systems that rely heavily on shelter registries.

Several comparative studies (Allen et al., 2020; Benjaminsen et al., 2020) assess the effectiveness of national strategies in countries such as Finland, Denmark, and Ireland. These countries are often cited for their integration of the Housing First model into homelessness policy and for advancing

systematic data collection methods. For example, Finland's long-term approach, which incorporates municipal-level data collected since 1987, is considered a best practice model (Benjaminsen et al., 2020).

COST Action 15218 (COST, 2021), has been another milestone in harmonizing data collection across Europe, offering scientific groundwork for developing comparable indicators. Complementing these efforts, Drilling (2020) and Hermans (2024) investigate city-level initiatives, noting the growing role of municipalities in direct service provision and data generation.

Researchers such as Coumans et al. (2017) explore advanced methodologies like the capture-recapture technique, applied in the Netherlands, as a means of estimating the hidden homelessness population not reached by traditional counts. These innovations underscore the need for triangulated approaches that blend administrative data, surveys, and point-in-time counts.

3 Definitions and Data Collection Methods

This section summarizes the main definitions used by the EU countries and the challenges associated with using multiple definitions.

3.1 Definitions of Homelessness in the European Context

Internationally, different definitions of homelessness have been developed so far; still, there is no convergence on the operationalisation and measurement of this phenomenon. The common trait is that homelessness has been generally considered a multidimensional concept.

In Europe, the European Federation of National Organisations Working with the Homeless (FEANTSA) has proposed the ETHOS (European Typology of Homelessness and Housing Exclusion) definition that relies on a three-domain home concept. The lack of at least two of these domains generates homelessness. Home is (i) a physical domain, i.e. a physical space over which a person and his/her family can exercise exclusive possession; a social domain in which individuals can preserve their privacy and enjoy social relations; a legal domain for which the individual has a legal title to occupation. This leads to the formulation of four concepts of Homelessness: Rooflessness, Houselessness, Insecure Housing and Inadequate Housing. ETHOS divides these four concepts into 13 operational categories used for classifying people who are experiencing homelessness according to their situation. A separate ETHOS definition, known as ETHOS 'Light', has also been formulated for statistical purposes, especially for homelessness data collection. Develtere (2022) points out that ETHOS 'Light' is a widely used and pragmatic tool for collecting homelessness data. ETHOS 'Light' focuses on the roofless and houseless because they are accepted as constituting homelessness in several European countries, differently from the categories of inadequate and insecure housing that are not fully included in the 'Light' definition. ETHOS 'Light' is the operative definition for the data collection on homelessness included in the recommendations of European

statisticians developed for the 2010/2011 population and housing censuses (UNECE and Eurostat, 2006). In these recommendations, people experiencing homelessness are grouped into two broad categories: primary and secondary homelessness. The former includes persons living in the streets without shelter; the latter includes persons with no usual residence who frequently move between various accommodations (including dwellings, shelters and institutions for people experiencing homelessness or other living quarters). This category includes persons living in private dwellings but reporting 'no usual address' on their census form.

For the 2021 census round, European statistical legislation stipulates that MS must do a separate counting of people experiencing homelessness. The recommendations for the 2021 censuses were largely revised compared to those of the previous census and simplified by reducing the number of categories. In particular, people experiencing primary homelessness were grouped with those experiencing secondary homelessness. The new aggregate categories are intended to simplify reporting while ensuring that this aggregate group's total count and essential characteristics are included in the census population, as explicitly required in the Regulation (EU) 2017/712. Countries can choose the appropriate census method, such as traditional enumeration surveys and register-based systems. However, Regulation (EU) 2017/712 requires the sources and methodology applied to produce data on people experiencing homelessness to be described in the metadata (Eurostat, 2019).

Despite the recommendations for 2021 censuses, as will become apparent in Section 4, comparing homeless data collection methods across EU MS is still tricky as countries define and measure homelessness differently.

3.2 Methodologies for Data Collection in Europe

As mentioned in Section 2, several studies have addressed the challenge of monitoring homelessness through the collection of quantitative data.

Counting the population experiencing homelessness is a difficult task because of the lack of a clear definition of homelessness, the mobility of the population, and the temporary or cyclical nature of homelessness for some individuals. As Pleace and Hermans (2020) point out, homeless people can be counted via contact with social protection or social housing systems that record details of applicants' living situation. An alternative way to count homeless people is the use of dedicated surveys or within sample surveys of the whole population.

Different data collection methods may capture different population groups as well as aspects of someone experiencing homelessness and their housing situation. For example, point-in-time counts are often conducted by volunteers who survey individuals experiencing homelessness on a specific day or night. They provide a snapshot of homelessness within a given community. Point-in-time counts are useful for identifying individuals living on the streets or in temporary shelters but may miss those who are temporarily staying with family friends or living in their cars. Several European countries use point-in-time counts to assess and monitor homelessness in their respective territories. In Ireland, the Dublin Region

Homeless Executive (DRHE) conducts a biennial rough sleeper count in Dublin. The French government conducts an annual point-in-time count known as “*La Nuit de la Solidarité*” (The Night of Solidarity) to assess street homelessness in Paris and other major cities, while some cities, such as Brussels and Milan, conduct regular street counts to estimate the number of people experiencing homelessness. City counts are also run in Bratislava (Slovakia) and Budapest (Hungary) according with Drilling et al (2020).

The capture and recapture method for estimating homelessness is not as widely used in EU MS compared to point-in-time counts or other methodologies. It is used by the National Statistical Institute in the Netherlands to estimate the number of individuals experiencing homelessness (Coumans et al., 2017). The method involves two or more independent “captures” of the persons experiencing homelessness from different sources, such as service providers, shelters, and outreach teams. After a defined period, the same sources recapture data and identify individuals who were previously counted in the initial capture. The overlap of identified individuals between the two sources is used to estimate the total population experiencing homelessness size through statistical modelling. This method accounts for potential undercounting in traditional counting methods as it misses out those individuals who are not included in administrative registries. However, it requires careful planning, coordination, and data sharing between different agencies or organizations involved in the data collection process.

Surveys and interviews can provide more detailed information about individuals experiencing homelessness. Questions can be tailored to capture various forms of homelessness, including living with family or friends, or staying in a vehicle. The methods allow for more detailed data collection but may be limited by sample size or potential biases in self-reporting.

Administrative data, such as registries maintained by shelters and local authorities can provide valuable information on individuals using homeless services and their transitions in and out of homelessness over time. These data sources can track the duration of stays, patterns of return, and the effectiveness of interventions. This information can be crucial for planning resources and designing targeted interventions to address homelessness. However, relying solely on shelter and service-based registries has limitations. These data sources may underrepresent certain populations, such as unsheltered individuals or those who do not engage with homeless services for various reasons. Several studies, such as Baptista and Marlier (2019), Bretherton and Mayock (2021), have shown that women may be less likely to turn to shelters as their first option. Instead, they may seek temporary housing arrangements with friends or family. Consequently, relying solely on shelter registries may not capture the full extent of homelessness among women or other population groups as young individuals or LGBTQI+ or families with children (inter alia Develtere, 2022).

Most of the countries do not collect information on all municipalities. Denmark, France, and Spain, for example, consider municipalities with at

least 20,000 inhabitants. The results are then weighted to represent a whole. It is crucial to have a high participation rate of survey to municipalities to get a complete national number of people in a homelessness situation. A general weakness of the data collection is that even if the municipalities are given instructions, the practices and sources to gather data vary between municipalities and are not always well documented (Allen et al., 2020).

Usually, homelessness is measured by a rate per 1,000 population to allow the comparability between geographical areas and/or periods that have different population size. In addition to provide a count of people experiencing homelessness, most EU MS collect information to draw the social and demographic profile, the living conditions and the difficulties that people experiencing homelessness have in gaining access to accommodation. The sociodemographic characteristics usually collected are sex, age, duration of residence in the country, nationality, accommodation (frequency, types, characteristics, previous cases and searching), economic situation, education, health, family links and history, the utilization of Social services and the relationship with Justice.

It is important to note that no single data collection method can perfectly capture the complexity and diversity of homelessness experience. Combining multiple approaches and engaging various stakeholders can help develop a more comprehensive understanding of housing solutions for people experiencing homelessness.

Finally, a specific form of homelessness, which is more difficult to address, is hidden homelessness. It refers to people whose living situation corresponds to one of the categories outlined in the ETHOS Light typology but who do not appear in official statistics on homelessness (Develtere, 2022). These individuals may be “couch surfing”, staying temporarily with friends or family, living in overcrowded or substandard accommodations, or residing in insecure housing situations which are more difficult to monitor. Understanding and addressing hidden homelessness requires a broader perspective and comprehensive approaches which include extending the range of services included in the assessment for example including also low threshold services, neighbourhood centres, public transport, regular social services, social housing providers, hospitals and mental health services, reception centres for asylum seekers and shelters for victims of domestic abuse and also extending data collection to people living in communities, where shelters and social support services might be less prevalent (Hermans, 2024).

4 Methodology

In order to investigate the dimensions of homelessness in European countries, this paper employs a qualitative data analysis methodology inspired by the interactive model developed by Miles and Huberman (1994). There are different versions of this model. Among those, the one followed in this paper is articulated in four different phases interacting throughout the analysis: (i) data collection, (ii) data reduction, (iii) data display, and (iv) drawing and verifying conclusions (Figure 1).

- Data collection is the systematic process of gathering information from various sources, such as institutional reports, legal documents, and scientific publications, to find answers to research questions. In this work, information has also been collected by emailing national institutes of statistics and experts of public institutions.

- Data reduction is the translation of information from one form to another without significant loss of information. The reduction helps to make information more accessible to comprehend and work with. The final goal is to create a consolidated picture through editing, segmenting, and summarising the unstructured data. Also, conceptualising and explaining is a way of reducing the data (Tesch, 1990).

- Data display is the process of presenting and analysing the data. The two forms used in this work to display information are the narrative text and tables reporting qualitative data. The latter enables information to be visually organised and summarised.

- Concluding logically follows the reduction and display of data. Given the expansion of this work's geographical scope, the conclusion will be verified by validating the information with the primary stakeholders in the field.

Figure 1. Components of Data Analysis: Interactive Model

Source: Miles and Huberman, (1994)

As the paper aims to address key questions regarding homelessness policies and data collection methodologies in EU MS, it focuses on examining the following items:

- existence of a general framework for homelessness with a legal definition in each of the European country;
- existence of a national strategy;
- leading authorities and stakeholders concerned;
- systematic national count carried out at the local level;
- specific assessments at the local level;
- periodicity of the count;
- draw of a socio-demographic profile of people experiencing homelessness.

5 Results

The findings and their implications should be discussed in the broadest context possible. Future research directions and potential policy implications may also be highlighted.

In this section, we provide a summary of the evidence gathered. This is schematically reported in Figure 2 and described in more detail in Tables A1.1-A1.2 in the Appendix. The first result concerns that essential disparities persist between EU MS in measuring/monitoring homelessness. Only 15 out of 27 MS have a legal definition of homelessness, and 16 have a national strategy to reduce homelessness. A legal definition of homelessness refers to a specific and legally recognized description of what constitutes homelessness within a particular jurisdiction. This definition identifies individuals eligible for homelessness assistance, support, and protection under the law. However, it is worth noting that while 15 EU MS have a legal definition of homelessness and 16 have national strategies, there are still variations in the comprehensiveness and effectiveness of these definitions and measures. Continuous evaluation, feedback loops, and sharing of best practices across MS can help improve the monitoring strategies and outcomes in addressing homelessness throughout the EU. As regards the existence of a systematic national count of people experiencing homelessness, it is worth mentioning that it has not been possible to obtain reliable information for Cyprus, the Czech Republic and Latvia. For the other 24 countries, 19 systematically collect data on homelessness, while five countries do not have a national count. It is noted that systematic data collection on homelessness involves a well-organized process of gathering, analysing, and interpreting information about individuals experiencing homelessness. The 19 countries systematically collecting data on homelessness have an operative definition of homelessness reported in Table A2 in the Appendix. These definitions vary in scope and specificity, ranging from broad to more narrowly focused. In some countries like Denmark, Finland and the Netherlands, the operative definition

encompasses a wide range of situations and living conditions that indicate a lack of stable housing (however, in the Netherlands, whole parts of the population experiencing homelessness are not counted -- older people experiencing homelessness for instance, or economically homeless). These definitions include individuals who are sleeping rough, living in emergency shelters, residing in temporary accommodations, and staying with friends or family. All the other countries, except for Spain, adopt definitions that focus on specific situations, such as people sleeping rough. Usually, these definitions distinguish between primary homelessness (sleeping rough) and secondary homelessness (temporary accommodations). In Spain, the operative definition focuses on the tenure aspect of homelessness, considering whether an individual has a stable and secure place to live. This definition underscores that homelessness is not solely about lacking a physical shelter but also about housing quality.

The 19 countries that systematically collect data on homelessness employ various methods, briefly presented in Section 2.1 and reported in Table A2 in the Appendix. The specific approaches and frequency of data collection (reported in Table A2 in the Appendix) may differ from country to country according to priorities and available resources. Ireland is the country with the highest frequency of updating data monthly at the county level. Other seven countries – Austria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, the Netherlands and Portugal – collect data on homelessness annually at the municipality level. Lithuania and Portugal have only recently started collecting data on homelessness annually since 2018. For Portugal, data on 2020 are not available due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the same is true for the Netherlands, which did not publish homelessness data for 2019. In Denmark, homelessness is monitored every two years, and the data are reported mainly for cities with a population of more than 20,000. Sweden estimates homelessness every six years; the data are available at the municipality level. Croatia, Estonia, and Malta conduct a census of the population experiencing homelessness every ten years as part of its decennial population census. This provides a snapshot of the population experiencing homelessness in conjunction with the overall census. In Croatia and Estonia, the data are published at the municipality level, while in Malta, they are collected at the national level. Countries with a national count also provide a socio-demographic profile of people experiencing homelessness. For the five countries that do not have national counts (Belgium, Hungary, Luxemburg, Romania, and Slovenia), the reasons behind this could vary. It could be due to limited resources, lack of prioritization, political factors, or challenges specific to each country's context. Belgium, for example, does not have a legal definition, neither a national strategy nor a national count drawing a socio-demographic profile. This is likely because the responsibility for people experiencing homelessness is decentralised to the regions, and therefore, there is no need for a national strategy. However, there is some coordination plan at the national level focused on rough sleeping. However, the absence of a national count does not necessarily mean that these countries are unaware or unconcerned about homelessness. They may still have localized efforts,

regional data, or alternative means of addressing homelessness within their regions or cities. In Belgium, a census is conducted annually at the municipality level only in the regions involved by the King Baudouin Foundation. In Hungary, a survey was conducted by service providers for individuals experiencing homelessness in 1999. This initiative is known as the “3rd of February workgroup”. Luxembourg planned to set up a regular physical count of people experiencing homelessness on the whole territory of Luxembourg. The first census of people experiencing homelessness took place only in the city of Luxembourg on 26 October 2022. However, the Ministry of Family and Integration has published reports with information provided by social service providers twice a year since 2012. In Romania, neither the government nor any association collects periodic data, so very little information is available—only the number of people entering night shelters. The same is true in Slovenia, where there is no national count of people experiencing homelessness. The existing data is the data on the users of services for people experiencing homelessness limited to services funded by the Ministry of Labour, Family and Social Affairs.

Limitations to this assessment includes the difficulty in gathering up to date information on all EU countries, which frequently made information available only in their official language. Limitations also include the rapidly changing scenario in these last years, also due to major shocks such as COVID-19, increased cost of living, unaffordable housing and rising inflation and the war in Ukraine.

Figure 2. Overview of Findings per EU MS

COUNTRY	Austria	Belgium	Bulgaria	Croatia	Republic of Cyprus	Czech Republic	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Ireland	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Malta	Netherlands	Poland	Portugal	Romania	Slovakia	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden
Legal national definition	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
National strategy	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
National monitoring programme at the local level	✓	✗	✓	✓	?	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	?	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓
Socio-demographic profile	✓	✗	✓	✓	?	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	?	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓

Source: the authors

6 Conclusions

This paper aimed to analyze how EU MS monitor homelessness and assess whether local dimensions are incorporated in this monitoring.

Additionally, it provides insights into national strategies to eradicate homelessness.

The findings indicate that most EU MS monitor homelessness as part of broader efforts to address social challenges and support vulnerable populations. Several EU countries made significant progress in recent years in measuring homelessness, a trend noted by Hermans at the conclusion of the COST Action 15218 project (Hermans, 2020). However, challenges remain in harmonizing data collection methodologies, definitions, frequency, and reporting practices across all MS. To address these issues effectively, Bush-Geertsema (2010) suggests fostering transnational exchange and cooperation, coupled with regular reporting requirements for member states.

To improve data collection, several recommendations can be proposed for EU countries:

- Develop a clear, comprehensive and standardized definition of homelessness that aligns with international standards, such as ETHOS.
- Adopt an expanded and robust data collection system to capture accurate and up-to-date information on homelessness, including “hidden homelessness”.
- Promote data-sharing partnerships and innovative approaches, such as integrating homelessness data with relevant sources like housing, migration, employment, health, and education data. This integration can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the underlying factors and consequences of homelessness.
- Engage people experiencing homelessness through participatory research, which can empower them, enhance data accuracy, and provide deeper insights into their needs.

Additionally, longitudinal studies are needed to track changes in homelessness, identify effective interventions, and evaluate the long-term impact of policies.

To further improve the effectiveness of efforts to combat homelessness and achieve sustainable development, it is crucial to integrate homelessness monitoring into policymaking for the 2030 Agenda, which encompasses the SDGs. This is particularly important for ensuring the implementation of the Leave-No-One-Behind principle (United Nation, 2015) and for supporting people in vulnerable situations (Denti, 2022). The Semester process and the European Platform on Combatting Homelessness provide frameworks for collecting European homelessness data and for fostering strategies to address this issue.

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Appendix

Table A1: Institutional aspects related to homelessness in the EU Member States

Country	National framework Legal national definition of homelessness National strategy	Main authorities and stakeholders concerned (specify)
1. Austria	<p>In Austria, there is no specific legal definition of homelessness that is applied throughout the country. Various laws and regulations in Austria provide the legal basis for homelessness-related matters. The Right to housing is not constitutionally guaranteed. However, it is established in legislation through the Austrian Social Aid Act (§20); which supports “homeless people and persons in extraordinary precarious situations” through the “provision of housing”. In Austria the registration of persons without fixed residence is possible with the instrument of the "main residence confirmation" (§ 19a, Reporting Act). This main residence confirmation enables homeless people to prove the centre of their life-relationship in the respective municipality area. The issuing of the main residence confirmation by the registry office is bound to two prerequisites: (1) it must be shown probably because that the centre of the life-relations has existed exclusively in the municipal territory for at least one month, and (2) the designation of a contact point, which is regularly visited by the homeless person. The contact point shall also be regarded as a mailing address, provided this is approved by the contact point. In Austria, there is no national strategy to prevent, fight or end homelessness, but some provinces of Austria have established regional support systems for the homeless.</p>	<p>Austrian Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection.</p>
2. Belgium	<p>No national legal definition A definition can be found in the regulation of the Brussels Joint Community Commission regarding emergency aid to and integration of homeless persons of 2018. The definition is the following: “1 homeless person: a person who is in one or more of the following situations:</p>	<p>Joint Community Commission; Wallon Region including Walloon Brabant; Brussels-Capital Region</p>

	<p>a) living in public spaces; b) does not have housing, is unable to obtain housing by his own means and therefore has no place to stay; c) does not have a dwelling that is habitable according to health, safety and habitability standards”</p> <p>Another definition can be found in the Cooperation Agreement relating to homeless people of 12 May 2014 between different governments: “Homelessness: situation where a person does not have his own dwelling, does not have the means to get one on his own and therefore does not have a place of residence, or temporarily stays in a place while waiting for his own place of residence to be made available to him.”</p> <p>These definitions are based on the ETHOS typology (European Typology on Homelessness and Housing Exclusion), and divide homeless people in different categories, including people who live on the street, people in emergency shelters, people who are about to leave an institution etc.</p> <p>No national strategy to reduce homelessness. In 2014, a cooperation agreement was signed by the federal state, the communities and the regions to coordinate policies of the different policy levels to prevent and to combat homelessness. According to Hermans 2017 it can be considered as the Belgian national action plan to combat homelessness. Following this agreement launched new policy measures launched for example the Integrated Action Plan to Prevent and Combat Homelessness 2020-24 (Flanders), Source OECD.</p>	
<p>3. Bulgaria</p>	<p>Formal definition of homelessness in the Social and Solidarity Act only at the end of 2018 (October 2018).¹</p> <p>People living rough, in emergency accommodation, and in accommodation for the homeless are considered homeless people.</p>	<p>Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works.</p> <p>According to the National Strategy, municipalities are expected to have</p>

¹ Enterprises of Social and Solidarity Economy Act. Retrieved from: <https://www.lex.bg/bg/laws/ldoc/2137187968>

	Homelessness has been identified as an important avenue for improvement in the 2020 national strategy for reducing poverty and promoting social inclusion 2030. ²	reliable mechanisms for data gathering, needs analysis, urban planning
4. Croatia	<p>Legal definition in the Social Care Act (NN 157/13, 152/14, 99/15, 52/16, 16/17, 130/17) approved in 2013:</p> <p>A homeless person is a person who has no place of residence, who resides in public place, or another place not intended for housing, and who has no means of meeting his/her housing needs.³</p> <p>Homelessness is addressed in the national Strategy for Combating Poverty and Social Exclusion (Bežovan, 2019). This strategy focuses partly on homeless services: shelters for homeless people, soup kitchens, social housing, development of employment programmes, and access to all the necessary services through programmes aimed at strengthening people’s capacities for independent living.</p>	<p>Government of the Republic of Croatia, Standing Committee for Social Services.</p> <p>Association of Towns and Municipalities.</p> <p>Croatian Network for the Homeless NGOs working with homeless people (e.g. Caritas charity of the Zagreb Archdiocese),</p> <p>Homeless shelters (e.g. Red Cross Homeless Shelter)</p>
5. Republic of Cyprus	<p>No official definition of homelessness.</p> <p>Definition used by the Council of Community Volunteering of the municipality of Germasogeia (in relation to the building of a temporary accommodation centre for the homeless):</p> <p>Homelessness includes cases of persons without secure housing or persons who live in rough conditions. Homeless persons are all those living legally in the country and without or with only insecure access to adequate owned or rented housing (adequate housing is housing that fulfils all the necessary requirements and has the basic water and electricity amenities). In particular, people living</p>	<p>Social Welfare Services</p> <p>Council of Community Volunteerism of Germasogeia</p>

² <https://www.mlsp.government.bg/uploads/40/sv/nsnbns-2030-en.pdf>

³ <https://www.zakon.hr/z/222/Zakon-o-socijalnoj-skrbi>

	<p>rough on the street, in temporary facilities or who are temporarily hosted in the homes of relatives are regarded as homeless, as well as those living in inadequate accommodation.</p> <p>No national strategy for reducing homelessness.</p>	
<p>6. Czech Republic</p>	<p>The International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights given legal effect in Czech law consists of some clauses which recognise the rights of everyone to an adequate standard of living including sufficient nutrition, clothing, healthcare and housing (Article 11).</p> <p>Czech law does not provide a unique definition of homelessness. The following definitions are used in different legal acts:</p> <p>Act No. 40/1993 (§ 3): a homeless person is defined as a person without state citizenship.</p> <p>Act No. 133/2000 (§ 10): a homeless person is someone whose permanent place of residence is the registration office in the district in which the person was born.</p> <p>Act No. 108/2006 (§ 57, 61, 63, 69) a homeless person is defined as a person in difficult social circumstances in connection with having lost her/his housing' (§ 57).</p> <p>In the Social Inclusion Strategy 2021-2030 homelessness is referred to by using the ETHOS typology</p> <p>No national strategy for reducing homelessness, but some municipalities have their own strategies.</p>	<p>The Ministry of Regional Development is responsible for regional and housing policies including their financing and distributing tasks between regional authorities, municipalities, and ministries.</p> <p>The Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs is responsible for (1) the provision of housing employment and social care (2) the design of medical insurance scheme (3) the funding of social service and social benefits and (4) awareness involvement and cooperation between all the stakeholders.</p> <p>Regional authorities and municipalities are obliged to collaborate to formulate a medium-term plan for the development of social services.</p>

		Major Czech cities are beginning to address homelessness and are looking for tools and strategies to improve the situation
7. Denmark	<p>Homeless people are defined as persons with special social problems, who are without - or are unable to live in - an independent apartment, and who are in need of a place to stay and for offers of activating support, care and subsequent assistance (Law on social services, § 94)</p> <p>In 2017, the Government introduced a National Strategy to reduce homelessness 2018-2021 that consists of 4 focus points and 15 initiatives:</p> <p>Focus 1: National use of evidence-based practice (National Guidelines)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Social investment fund into homelessness (investment in progressive preventive initiatives with a holistic focus, with the aim to reduce long-term cost for the municipalities) 2. National guidelines for homelessness 3. National guidelines for initiatives towards ending homelessness <p>Focus 2: Strengthen the prevention of homelessness</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Housing First for youth 5. Youth Housing with support from social worker, established in already existing places for young people 6. Prevention of evictions 7. An overall scheme for financial- and debt counselling <p>Focus 3: An easier way out of homelessness</p>	<p>Main authorities and stakeholders concerned:</p> <p>The National Board of Social Services published National guidelines for the fight against homelessness in 2020.⁴</p>

⁴ <https://socialstyrelsen.dk/udgivelser/nationale-retningslinjer-for-indsatsen-modhjemloshed/@@download/publication>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Strengthen the cooperation of shelters and municipalities, to make permanent accommodation available for the sheltered person. 9. Simple, minimized and flexible connection to job centre, case manager, etc. 10. Support for citizens in long term homelessness 11. Outreach Psychiatry 12. Revision of the 'crooked housing' scheme (single barracks for long term homeless) 13. Better information and securing of homeless rights – support for user organizations <p>Focus 4: Other</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Explore on women and homelessness 2. Support for emergency-shelters (night shelters during the winter) 	
<p>8. Estonia</p>	<p>There is no official definition of homelessness in Estonian legislation.</p> <p>The State does not have a national strategy</p> <p>Homelessness is primarily addressed through the Social Welfare Act, which provides a framework for social support and assistance to individuals and families in need, including those experiencing homelessness.</p> <p>The Social Welfare Act⁵ establishes the obligation of local municipalities to provide support and assistance to individuals facing social difficulties, including homelessness. Municipalities are responsible for ensuring access to emergency accommodation, social housing, and other necessary support services for homeless individuals.</p> <p>Additionally, the Estonian government has implemented several programs and initiatives to address homelessness, such as the Housing Allowance Act, which aims to provide financial assistance to individuals and families to secure suitable housing.</p>	<p>Central government; municipalities.</p>

⁵ The complete act in English can be found here: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/519012023005/consolide/current>.

<p>9. Finland</p>	<p>A person is considered homeless if does not have her/his own home (rented or owned residence) and if she/he lives: 1) outside, in stairways or temporary shelters; 2) in dormitories or hostels; 3) in welfare home-type housing units, rehabilitation units, hospitals or other institutions; 4) temporarily with friends or relatives due to lack of housing.</p> <p>The Finnish National Homelessness Strategy covers the Paavo I and Paavo II programs, which took place between 2008–2011 and 2012–2015. Paavo I and Paavo II programs involve elected local governments from 10 cities, including the capital Helsinki which had the highest levels of homelessness. They signed letters of intent which committed them into the Paavo I and Paavo II programs and had them working in coordination with central government. This created a context in which all levels of government in Finland and all major administrative bodies that were required for a coherent integrated national strategy were in place.</p> <p>The Action Plan for Preventing Homelessness in Finland (2016-2019) main goal was continuing to reduce homelessness.</p> <p>Instead the Programme to end long-term homelessness by 2027, aims at eliminate long-term homelessness by 2027 by support to housing and extensive cooperation between administrative units</p>	<p>Main institutions involved: Ministry of the Environment, Ministry of Social Affairs, the Criminal Sanctions Agency, the Housing Finance and Development Centre of Finland (ARA), local governments</p>
<p>10. France</p>	<p>DALO law (Droit Au Logement Opposable) called High Committee for the Housing of People experiencing a condition of disadvantage: This monitoring committee can formulate proposals for the implementation of the right to housing. It gives its opinion on any matter which the Government needs. It prepares an annual report that is submitted to the President of the Republic, the Prime Minister and Parliament.</p> <p>DALO law provides a legal definition:</p> <p>People likely to be recognized under the enforceable right to housing must meet one or more of the following 7 conditions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No fixed place of residence 	<p>The national government created an inter-ministerial body in charge of developing, coordinating and monitoring the implementation of policies on homelessness (DIHAL), the responsibility for implementation is shared with regional and local authorities.</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Being at risk of eviction without rehousing 3. Being hosted either in a shelter (structure d’hébergement ou une résidence hôtelière à vocation sociale, RHVS) continuously for more than 6 months or in a temporary housing or a hostel accommodation since more than 18 months. 4. Living in a dangerous or unhealthy place, which is unsuitable for habitation. 5. Living in severely deprived housing that does not have the required equipment and comfort (lack of heating, drinking water, etc.), under the condition of having at least one minor child or a disabled person in the household. 6. Living in a house with a total floor area that is not greater than or equal to 16 m² for a couple without children. The size’s threshold increases by 9 m² per additional person within the limit of 70 m² for 8 people and more, under the condition that there is at least one minor child or a disabled person in the household. 7. Having applied for social housing since an abnormally long period (delay that varies with the region) without receiving an offer that meets the household needs. <p>There is in place the 2nd national plan for the housing first and combatting homelessness (2023-2027)</p>	
<p>11. Germany</p>	<p>During the reform of the federal system in 2006, the exclusive competence for housing law was transferred to the federal states. Yet, the federal Law on social housing (Gesetz über die Wohnraumförderung) is still in force but is not applicable in federal states which have passed new federal state laws on social housing.</p> <p>Section 1 of the federal Law on social housing mentions homeless persons as forming part of the target group of social housing. Yet, the regulations do not contain a definition of homelessness.</p> <p>A National Action Plan Against Homelessness is in place since 2024</p>	<p>Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building, and Community; State and Local Governments; Municipalities and City Administrations; Social Welfare Agencies</p>
<p>12. Greece</p>	<p>A definition of homelessness was written into Greece’s national legislation in 2012. Article 29 of Law 4052 includes two defining provisions. Firstly, the homeless are “all persons legally residing in the</p>	<p>The Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs, Ministry of Health, and</p>

	<p>country, that have no access, or have unsafe access to sufficient privately owned, rented or bestowed housing that meets the required specification and has basic water services and electricity.” Secondly, the term homeless includes those who live in temporary institutions, hostels, on the street, or “other inappropriate accommodation.”</p> <p>The National Action Plan to combat homelessness covers the period 2023-2027</p>	<p>Ministry of Interior, are responsible for implementing policies and programs to address homelessness, providing funding, and coordinating efforts with other stakeholders.</p> <p>Local municipalities have a significant role in managing homelessness within their jurisdictions. They often establish homeless shelters, outreach programs, and collaborate with local organizations to provide services and support for individuals experiencing homelessness.</p>
<p>13. Hungary</p>	<p>The legal definition of homelessness can be found in Act CXXIX of 2013 on the Rules of Public Order. According to this law, a homeless person is defined as someone who lacks a permanent residence and resides in a public space, a temporary shelter, or an institution providing temporary accommodation without having the right to use it as a permanent residence.</p> <p>The State does not have a national strategy</p>	<p>The Ministry of Human Capacities; government agencies; municipalities.</p> <p>The Ministry of Human Capacities is responsible for social welfare policies, including homelessness.</p> <p>Government agencies develop and implement policies, allocate</p>

		<p>funding, and coordinate efforts to address homelessness.</p> <p>Municipalities have a significant role in managing homelessness within their jurisdictions. They are responsible for implementing government policies, providing social services, and coordinating local initiatives to address homelessness. They often collaborate with NGOs and other stakeholders to develop and implement local strategies.</p>
<p>14. Ireland</p>	<p>The legal definition of homelessness is outlined in the Housing Act 1988, as amended by the Housing (Miscellaneous Provisions) Act 2009 and the Housing (Homeless Prevention) Act 2014. The legislation defines a homeless person as someone who:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has no accommodation that they have a legal right to occupy, either alone or with others. • Has accommodation but cannot secure entry to it. • Has accommodation, but their living conditions are such that it is considered unfit for habitation. <p>Additionally, a person may be considered homeless if she/he is living in a hospital, institution, or a temporary accommodation provided by a housing authority. However, the definition of homelessness may vary slightly across different jurisdictions within Ireland, as the country is divided</p>	<p>Government; Non-Governmental Organizations; municipalities.</p>

	<p>into local authority areas, and each local authority may have its own specific guidelines and procedures for addressing homelessness.</p> <p>The Programme for Government, "Our Shared Future" (2016-2021) commits to reducing and preventing homelessness and provides detail on how the Government will approach this challenge. One key issue to resolve homelessness is to increase the supply of housing, particularly for those on the lowest incomes. To this end, the Programme for Government commits to the increased supply of public, social and affordable homes. In particular, it will increase the social housing stock by more than 50,000 with an emphasis on new builds. Overall, the Programme aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase funding and work with stakeholders, caseworkers and homeless people on a suite of measures to channel rough sleepers into sustainable accommodation. • Continue to expand the Housing First approach with a focus on the construction and acquisition of one-bed homes and the provision of relevant supporting services. • Ensure the HSE provides a dedicated funding line and resources to deliver the necessary health and mental health supports required to assist homeless people with complex needs. • Ensure Rent Supplement and Housing Assistance Payment (HAP) levels are adequate to support vulnerable households while we increase the supply of social housing. • Move away from dormitory-style accommodation on a long-term basis and aim to provide suitable tenancies. • Ensure that aftercare and transition plans and protocols are developed for vulnerable homeless people or those at risk of homelessness leaving hospital, State care, foster care, prison or other State settings. • Develop a National Youth Homelessness Strategy. • Continue the Housing Agency's Acquisition Fund to purchase vacant stock from financial institutions. 	
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase funding for drug free hostels. • Continue to fund the Mortgage Arrears Resolution Service. <p>In 2021 a new Housing Plan for Ireland was launched “Housing for All. For homeless the plan aims at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increased ‘Housing First’ targets to 1,200 occupancies over five years • Nominate a new National Homeless Action Committee • Provide personalised Integrated Healthcare 	
<p>15. Italy</p>	<p>There is no official definition of homelessness in Italian legislation. Regional and local governments may have their own specific regulations and definitions regarding homelessness and related social services.</p> <p>The current national programmes and financial resources are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. National plan of interventions and social services 2021-2023;⁶ 2. Programme for Social Inclusion 2021-2027;⁷ 3. National Recovery and Resilience Plan (Mission 5, component #3)⁸ <p>The Ministry of Labour and Social Policy have committed to paying special attention to homelessness during the period of 2014-2020. Homelessness is recognized as urgent issue within National Anti-Poverty Plan (ESF) to address two priorities: reducing homelessness; making Housing First as the first way to tackle homelessness.</p> <p>Several actions but no national strategy to reduce homelessness.</p>	<p>Ministry of Labour and Social Policies; Ministry of Interior: regional councils; municipal governments.</p>

⁶ <https://www.lavoro.gov.it/priorita/Documents/Piano-Nazionale-degli-Interventi-e-dei-Servizi-Sociali-2021-2023.pdf>

⁷ <https://poninclusionelavoro.gov.it/PN-2021-2027/Pagine/default>

⁸ <https://politichecoesione.governo.it/it/pnrr-e-coesione/la-missione-5-m5-componente-3-del-pnrr-su-interventi-speciali-per-la-coesione-territoriale/>

	In 2014, the Italian government introduced a law called "Decreto del Fare" (Decree of Doing) which defined a "housing emergency" (emergenza abitativa) as a situation where a person lacks a suitable and stable housing solution. This law aimed to address housing issues, particularly for vulnerable individuals and families.	
16. Latvia	The legal definition of homelessness may vary depending on the context and the specific laws in place. Generally, homelessness refers to the condition of individuals or families who lack a fixed, regular, and adequate night-time residence. There is no national homelessness strategy in Latvia; services are provided within the social policies framework (Social Services and Social Assistance Law).	Ministry of Welfare; municipalities; social welfare departments.
17. Lithuania	There is no official definition of homelessness in Lithuanian legislation. There is not yet a specific national strategy regarding homelessness and housing exclusion in Lithuania.	Ministry of Social Security and Labour; municipalities.
18. Luxembourg	The definition of homelessness is in the law of social inclusion of 19 July 2013 (loi relative à l'inclusion sociale). The national government approved a national strategy against homelessness and housing exclusion for the period 2013-2020. This strategy provided a framework for the actions undertaken by different government institutions to combat all forms of homelessness and housing exclusion. ⁹	The main institutions involved are the Ministry of Family Affairs, Integration and the Greater Region. ¹⁰
19. Malta	Malta lacks: (i) a formal definition of homelessness and of housing exclusion; and (ii) an overarching strategy to combat homelessness and housing exclusion.	

⁹ <https://mfamigr.gouvernement.lu/dam-assets/publications/rapport-etude-analyse/etat-des-lieux-sans-abrisme/Evaluation-intermediaire-strategie-sans-abrisme.pdf>

¹⁰ <https://mfamigr.gouvernement.lu/en/publications/plan-strategie/sdf.html>

<p>20. Netherlands</p>	<p>The authorities in the Netherlands (Department of Health, Welfare and Sport, central local authorities) have not formally established a definition of homelessness for policy aims.</p> <p>There is a national programme that aims to reduce homelessness among youth (aged 18-27) (Actieprogramma Dak- en thuisloze jongeren 2019-2021), as well as a strategic policy agenda established by governmental and non-governmental parties to deal with homelessness (Meerjarenagenda beschermd wonen en maatschappelijke opvang).</p>	<p>Department of Health, Welfare and Sport, local authorities.</p>
<p>21. Poland</p>	<p>The formal definition of a homeless person in Poland was adopted in the Social Welfare Act of 2004. A person is considered as homeless if he/she does not live in an apartment in the meaning of the provisions on the protection of tenants' rights and is not registered for permanent residence in the understanding of the provisions on the population register; it is also a person who despite being registered cannot live in an apartment (Act 32004).</p> <p>Article 75 of the Polish Constitution states that public authorities pursue policy aimed at satisfying the housing needs of citizens and preventing homelessness by supporting social housing or supporting citizens' efforts to obtain their own housing.</p> <p>In 2022 Poland approved a national strategy focusing on social services and public policies which also cover homelessness.</p>	<p>Ministry of Family, Labour, and Social Policy; the Ministry of Infrastructure and Construction; municipalities.</p>
<p>22. Portugal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition provided by the National Strategy for the Integration of Homeless People 2017-2023: A homeless person is considered to be an individual who, regardless of his/her nationality, racial or ethnic origin, religion, age, sex, sexual orientation, socio-economic status and mental and physical health, is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) roofless and living in a public space or insecure form of shelter or accommodated in an emergency shelter, or 	<p>Ministry of Labor, Solidarity, and Social Security; municipalities.</p>

	<p>ii) is houseless and living in temporary accommodation for the homeless.</p> <p>The definition of homelessness in Portugal is clearly linked to the European typology of homelessness and housing exclusion (ETHOS). It includes categories 1, 2, 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5 of ETHOS Light – that is, those who are roofless and living in a public space or insecure form of shelter, or accommodated in an emergency shelter, as well as those who are houseless and living in temporary accommodation for the homeless.</p> <p>The National Strategy for the Inclusion of People Experiencing Homelessness covers the period 2025-2030.</p> <p>The National Strategy was developed by a structure involving various stakeholders such as State departments, public entities, municipalities, NGOs, civil society and security forces. The coordination of the National Strategy implementation was committed to the Institute of Social Security.</p>	
23. Romania	<p>In Romania, the Social Work Law 292 / 2011 provides the legal definition of homelessness.</p> <p>The homeless people represent a social category formed by individuals or families who, because of single or combined social, medical, economic, judicial reasons or due to extreme situations, live on the streets, live temporarily at friends or acquaintances, are unable to maintain rented housing or they are at risk of eviction, they live in institutions or prisons from where they are to be discharged in the following two months and they do not have a home or a residence (Law 292, 2011).</p> <p>The country has a National Strategies covering the period 2022-2027.</p>	<p>Ministry of Labour and Social Justice; Ministry of Health; municipalities.</p>
24. Slovakia	<p>The Slovak legal system does not define homelessness but does define the tools for prevention and specific forms of support for this group of inhabitants.</p>	<p>Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, and Family; Ministry of Construction and Regional Development; municipalities and local governments.</p>

<p>25. Slovenia</p>	<p>In Slovenia there is no official definition of homelessness.</p> <p>National programmes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the 'National Programme of Social Care 2013-2020' (Resolution on the National Programme of Social Care for 2013-2020, 2013); 2) the 'National Housing Programme 2015-2025' (Resolution on the National Housing Programme 2015-2025, 2015). <p>The Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities follows the 2004 ETHOS definition of four conceptual categories of homeless people: roofless, houseless, in insecure housing, and in inadequate housing (including the operational sub-categories).</p>	<p>Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities; municipalities.</p>
<p>26. Spain</p>	<p>In Spain, there is no specific definition of homelessness that is universally applicable across all regions and municipalities. Various laws and regulation exist at the national level, as well as the local level (municipality) to protect the rights of homeless individuals and to provide social assistance, including access to housing and support services.</p> <p>The Comprehensive National Strategy for Homeless People 2015-2020. The strategy had 5 strategic objectives and 13 strategic lines.¹¹ The five objectives were:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Prevent homelessness. 2) Raise social awareness and defend against discrimination and hate crimes against the homeless. 3) Protect the lives of the homeless. 4) Restore life projects. 	<p>National government; the Ministry of Health; Social Services, and Equality; the Ministry of Labour and Social Economy; Regional and Local Governments.</p>

¹¹ <https://www.mdsocialesa2030.gob.es/derechos-sociales/servicios-sociales/Personas-sin-hogar/docs/StrategyHomeless20152020English.pdf>

	5) Reinforce services targeting the homeless provided by the public system and improve understanding, exchange of information and assessment.	
27. Sweden	<p>In Sweden, there is no specific legal definition of homelessness.</p> <p>Sweden has a national homelessness strategy for the period 2022-2026. It is a multifaceted strategy and recognizes prevention, outreach work, measures to combat acute forms of homelessness, and the role of Housing First.</p> <p>There are no national statistics about homeless people.</p> <p>Many municipalities, however, have launched their own municipal housing strategies and action plans to combat homelessness.</p> <p>The Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare has been carried out national mapping of homelessness in Sweden, commissioned by the Government.</p>	Central government; the Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare; municipalities.

Table A2: Count of homeless people in the EU Member States

Country	Local monitoring - Homeless operative definition	Local monitoring – Geographic unit (municipality / metropolitan area / district)	Local monitoring – Time frequency, timeliness	Local monitoring – Disaggregation (F/M, origin, disability, age & temporary, chronic, sporadic,)	Local monitoring – Stakeholders involved	Local monitoring – Methodology (information from the police, information from shelters, street count, homeless registered in the registry office, a combination of those)
1. Austria	The concept for measuring the indicator for registered homeless was	Municipality	Annually	Gender, age, education.	Statistics Austria	Data collection is based on a pseudonymized population register (“POPREG”, based on

	<p>fundamentally revised and improved for the report on integration indicators 2018 (Registrierte Obdach- und Wohnungslosigkeit) The new way of counting takes the European typology of homelessness, and precarious housing (ETHOS) as a starting point. Accordingly, the following categories from ETHOS can be recorded empirically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • people in shelters • people who live in institutions for the homeless • people who live in women's shelters 				<p>the central residence register (ZMR)). Statistics Austria combines two methods of counting homeless people: Homeless persons that have a specific register entry of homelessness (Hauptwohnsitzbestätigung). This refers to persons who can register themselves as homeless at the address of a contact point in a municipality where they can assure to have their center of living (this is also important for mail deliveries) Persons that live in an institution for homeless people according to the ETHOS categories 2 (People stay in a night shelter), 3 (People in accommodation for the homeless), 4 (People in Women's Shelter) and 7.1</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> people living in long-term accommodation for the elderly homeless. 					<p>(Residential care for homeless people).</p> <p>If a person is at least one day in a reference year registered as homeless according to the abovementioned methods 1) and/or 2) they are measured in the indicator on registered homelessness (double counting is prevented by a pseudonymized key).</p>
2.Belgium	<p>Homeless people are not represented in the official poverty statistics in Belgium. King Baudouin Foundation carries out a point-in-time census in part of the country.¹² Old count of homeless people made by SILC-CUT research funded</p>	<p>Municipality only in the regions involved by the King Baudouin Foundation.</p> <p>In 2022 census, the point-in-time count was made in 6 different regions.</p>	Annually	Age, health, education, employment status.	King Baudouin Foundation.	Point-in-time count.

¹² <https://kbs-frb.be/en/census-homeless-people>

	<p>by the Agora Research Programme of the Belgian Science Policy upon request from the 'Combat Poverty, Insecurity and Social Exclusion Service' (http://www.combatpoverty.be), which was established by the Federal Government, the Regions and Communities as an instrument in the fight against poverty, insecurity and social exclusion.</p> <p>http://www.belspo.be</p>					
3.Bulgaria	<p>During the 2021 Census, the National Statistical Institute of Bulgaria collected data on two types of homeless persons -</p>	<p>Count at the regional level (NUTS 3) for all municipalities</p>	<p>Ten years</p>	<p>Age; gender; education</p>	<p>National Institute of Statistics</p>	<p>The census methodology is based on a questionnaire for building, dwelling and population.</p>

	<p>primary and secondary homeless.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Homeless persons (without dwelling) - persons who live under the open sky due to lack of dwelling or other reasons. - Persons in a home for temporary accommodation of the homeless – dwellings where homeless persons are accommodated. 					
4. Croatia	<p>Definition for data collection provided by the National Institute of Statistics and used in the Census of Population, Households and Dwellings:</p>	Municipality	Ten years	Age, gender, education.	Data for official statistics are provided by the Ministry of	The Census enumerates homeless people in shelters or at places where enumerators found them.

	<p>A homeless person is defined as the person who, due to the lack of accommodation of his/her own, does not have any other options but to live on the street and without a conventional shelter that complies with the definition of the dwelling (Primary homeless (or roofless)), or a person who frequently resides in various types of accommodation such as shelters, institutions for the homeless or similar housing units (Secondary homeless (or houseless)).</p>				<p>Demography, Family, Youth and Social Policy.</p> <p>Croatian Homeless Network</p> <p>National Institute of Statistics</p>	
5. Republic of Cyprus	The Statistical Service of Cyprus does not	-	-	.	.	.

	have any information on the number of homeless persons in Cyprus.					
6. Czech Republic					Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs	
7. Denmark	<p>The definition, provided by ‘VIVE – The Danish Centre for Social Science Research’, includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rough sleepers • Emergency shelter use • Homeless shelters • Hotels etc. due to homelessness • Family and friends (Staying temporary and 	Municipality with at least 20,000 inhabitants	Two years	Gender, age, citizenship.	VIVE	<p>Figures based on a week count, always in week 6 in February, every second year, except in 2021 which was postponed to 2022 due to the pandemic.</p> <p>Homeless shelter users are identified by the CPR number, which is required when enrolling in a shelter. This allows to integrate data on homelessness with data from the Census.</p>

	<p>without a contract)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Short term transitional housing• Release from prison within one month without a housing solution• Discharge from hospital or treatment centre within one month without a housing solution• Other (e.g garden allotment house, camping wagons etc.)• Unknown homelessness situation					
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<p>8. Estonia</p>	<p>Statistics Estonia defined the concept of homelessness and agreed on it with Eurostat. The definition of the homeless in the 2021 census is as follows: the homeless can be persons who live in the streets and do not have housing that could be classified as a dwelling (primary homelessness) or persons moving frequently between temporary places of accommodation (secondary homelessness).</p>	<p>Municipality</p>	<p>10 years</p>	<p>Gender; age; nationality; location (municipality; county).</p>	<p>Statistics Estonia</p>	<p>Data on the homeless population are obtained from municipalities, data on nursing homes and special care homes from the Social Protection Information System, data on substitute homes from the Social Services and Benefits Data Register.¹³</p>
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¹³ The methodology is described in this document in English:

<https://www.stat.ee/sites/default/files/2022-06/Registrip%C3%B5hise%20loenduse%20metoodika%20raportEN.pdf>

<p>9. Finland</p>	<p>A person is considered homeless if they do not have their own home (rented or owned residence) and if they live: 1) outside, in stairways or temporary shelters; 2) in dormitories or hostels; 3) in welfare home-type housing units, rehabilitation units, hospitals or other institutions; 4) temporarily with friends or relatives due to lack of housing. Homelessness is considered long-term if it has lasted for at least one year or if the individual has repeatedly experienced</p>	<p>Municipality</p>	<p>Annually</p>	<p>Types of homelessness: Temporarily with friends or relatives; Outside, in stairwells, shelters, etc.; In dormitories or hostels; Institutional units. Women; Men; Young people (under 25); Immigrants</p>	<p>Survey carried out by the Housing Finance and Development Centre of Finland (governmental organisation)</p>	<p>Survey sent to all 293 municipalities in mainland Finland. The survey response rate was 80% in 2021. Municipalities collected data from social welfare and housing service registers and from the housing applicant registers of municipal rental housing companies. Some municipalities use Kela's Social Assistance Register or the Digital and Population Data Services Agency's Population Information Register to obtain and verify homelessness data.</p>
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	homelessness over the last three years. ¹⁴					
10. France	For survey purposes, a person is considered homeless if they spent the night preceding the survey interview in a shelter (collective facility, hotel room, or housing facility paid for by an association) or a place not intended or equipped for dwelling (on the street, in a squat etc.). ¹⁵	Municipality with at least 20,000 inhabitants	Last INSEE survey: 2012	Gender; age (18-29; 30-49; 50 years or more); born in France or not; income; education; type of household.	INSEE	Survey
11. Germany	The Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs divides homeless people into three categories: those	Municipality	Persons living in shelters are counted annually;	Gender, age, health problems (disability, long-term illness, addiction to drugs or alcohol), citizenship.	Federal Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs	

¹⁴ Source: [https://www.ara.fi/en-US/Materials/Homelessnessreports/HomelessnessinFinland2021\(63305\)](https://www.ara.fi/en-US/Materials/Homelessnessreports/HomelessnessinFinland2021(63305))

¹⁵ Source: <https://www.insee.fr/fr/metadonnees/definition/c1256>

	who are sheltered in emergency accommodation; those staying with friends; people who live on the streets.		persons living on the street or with friends are counted every two years.			
12. Greece	The first counting for homeless people took place in May 2018.	Seven main cities: Athens, Piraeus, Nea Ionia, Thessalonik, Ioannina, Trikala, Iraklion.	-	Gender; age, origin; related problems explaining homelessness (e.g. severe financial difficulty; unemployment).	Pilot activity designed by Panteion University and the Ministry of Labour, Social Insurance and Social Solidarity	Homeless people were counted through street count in two phases: phase A, night count and Phase B: day count via the existing programmes and structures supporting homeless people. Overall, 691 living in the street were counted, while 519 persons were living in shelters and 438 in apartments. ¹⁶

¹⁶ <https://www.feantsa.org/download/gr-country-profile-20188609335085222190081.pdf>

<p>13. Hungary</p>	<p>Since 1999 on the 3rd of February, a survey is conducted by service providers for homeless (3rd of February workgroup).</p> <p>The survey only covers those people who are in touch with shelters or outreach teams who volunteer to take part at the time of the survey.</p>	<p>Municipalities</p>	<p>Annually</p>	<p>Number of people living in shelters or in any other structure; number of people sleeping rough.</p>	<p>Service providers; Ministry of Social Affairs and Labour.</p>	<p>A survey is conducted among homeless people in Budapest and a growing number of municipalities.</p>
<p>14. Ireland</p>	<p>Homelessness data are collected by counties and published monthly by the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage of the Irish government.</p>	<p>County</p>	<p>Monthly</p>	<p>Age, gender, citizenship and the accommodation type where the single person is sleeping. The analysis considers separately adults (aged 18 or more) and families with children</p>	<p>Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage of the Irish</p>	<p>Data are collected counting adults and families accessing any kind of emergency accommodation during the last full week of every month. This means that people living rough and people living in inadequate housing for long periods are not taken into account for the</p>

					governme nt	purpose of this analysis. For this reason the numbers are underestimated and the extent of the phenomenon is probably bigger.
15. Italy	The first source is the National Institute of Statistic (Istat) that provide census data about homeless people since 2022. The Census identifies roofless and houseless - people living rough, in emergency accommodation, in accommodation for homeless.	Municipality	Annually	Age; gender; education; employment status.	Different sources deliver official statistics and overview on Homelessness in Italy. Among these, there are: 1. National Institute	The homeless population is included in the Italian census since 1991, however before 2021 data were collected with a “point in time” technique, it means counting people during one specific night in the main cities. In 2021 ISTAT (National institute of statistics) started using data from the civil registry, since homeless people are registered in the town where they habitually reside (law 1228/1954).

					<p>of Statistic (Istat)</p> <p>2. Italian Caritas</p> <p>3. Fio.PSD (Italian Federation of Organizations Working with Homeless People</p> <p>4. Fondazione Rodolfo Debenedetti</p>	<p>First national survey on Homeless People in Italy was conducted in 2011, the Follow up in 2014. The latter was conducted in 158 big and medium-sized Italian cities. It has not been repeated.</p>
16. Latvia	The Ministry of Welfare Republic of Latvia defines homeless people as	Municipality			Ministry of Welfare	

	those who lack a regular and adequate night time residence. This includes people who reside in emergency shelters, temporary accommodation facilities, or public spaces, such as streets, parks, and abandoned buildings, due to the absence of alternative housing options.				Republic of Latvia	
17. Lithuania	In 2021 census, homeless people are those who have no permanent place of residence and no money to rent or buy at least a basic lodging, and for this reason they live on the streets, in	Municipality	Annually since 2018	Gender	Statistics Lithuania	Number of people living in temporary care facilities. A homeless person is assigned to the address of the shelter for homeless people.

	places not appropriate for human habitation, in institutions for temporary living (night shelters).					
18. Luxembourg	At present, Luxembourg does not have accurate data on the extent of homelessness as homeless people are not statistically counted. To better determine the needs in the fight against homelessness, it is planned to set up a regular physical count of homeless people on the territory of Luxembourg. Since 2012, the Ministry of the Family and Integration publishes	City of Luxembourg but the next editions (planned for May and December 2023) should involve other municipalities.	Six months	Gender, age, health conditions.	Ministry of the Family and Integration	Street-count methodology. 66 social sector professionals were divided into 32 teams that walked the streets of the 24 city districts. Equipped with short concise questionnaires, they approached homeless people to get to know the better and listen to their needs.

	<p>reports twice a year with information provided by social service providers.</p> <p>On 26 October 2022 the first census of homeless people took place in the city of Luxembourg.</p>					
19. Malta	<p>The National Statistical Office defines a homeless as a person living on the street without a shelter.</p>	Country	Ten years	Age, gender, education.	National Statistical Office	<p>In the 2021 Census of population, also people living in shelter for homeless were included. This document reports a total of 88 people living in this kind of structure on a total population of 520.000 inhabitants. Apart from that, the only official data available, presented by the government in 2018, is the number of cases reported by the police regarding people sleeping rough.</p>

<p>20. Netherlands</p>	<p>Numbers of homelessness measured by Statistics Netherlands (CBS). According to CBS, homeless people are people who sleep in the open air, in indoor public spaces such as entrances, bicycle parks, train and bus stations, shopping malls or in cars, who spend the night indoors at community shelters, or temporarily stay with friends, acquaintances or relatives on a non-structural basis and without a fixed abode.</p>	<p>Municipality</p>	<p>Annually (data for 2019 are not available)</p>	<p>Gender, age (only people aged between 18 and 65 years are considered), place of living, origin.</p>	<p>Statistics Netherlands</p>	<p>The number of homelessness refer to registered homeless people receiving benefits under the Work and Social Assistance Act (WWB), people that have applied for low-threshold (night) shelter, as registered in the Personal Records Database (BRP), and some selected people from the National Drug and Alcohol information System (LADIS) (Rutenfrans- Stupar, 2019). Though, these sources exclude those homeless that sleep rough or those that are not eligible for social support services (those without Dutch nationality or those that have an income that is higher than a certain threshold) and thus figures of homelessness are extrapolated estimates. Capture-recapture methodology.</p>
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21. Poland		Region	Annually	Age, gender.	Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policy	Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policy collects data from all social welfare centres in Poland, including statistics on homeless assistance. The Ministry produces a biennial national study on homelessness.
22. Portugal	A person is considered roofless (sem teto) if he is living in public places, in emergency shelters or in precarious locations; while someone is considered houseless (sem casa) if he is living in temporary accommodations,	Municipality	Annually since 2018 except for 2020.	Age, gender, education, employment status	ENIPSSA	Survey conducted to comply with the necessity of clear and accessible data.
23. Romania	There is no national strategy to collect data on homeless people in Romania. In general, neither the government	-	-	-	-	-

	<p>nor any association collects periodic data, so very little information is available. Only the number of people entering in night shelters is available.</p>					
24. Slovakia	<p>The Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic conducted a population census in 2011. Homeless people are divided into four main groups by the effects on their living conditions. The first group consists of roofless (people living outside without a “roof” above their</p>	<p>District (the total number of districts is 79 that correspond to LAU 1)¹⁷.</p>	<p>10 years</p>	<p>Gender, age, nationality; education; marital status.</p>	<p>Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic</p>	<p>Concept and methodology of the census allowed for the quantification of the secondary homeless, residents who use different types of temporary accommodation and often move between accommodation such as a shelter, halfway home, emergency housing equipment or reside in non-conventional housing (recreational object; emergency object, not intended</p>

¹⁷ LAU is for Local Administrative Units that are levels below the NUTS (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) levels.

	<p>heads), the second represents houseless people (they are located in dormitories, day centres etc.). The third group is created by “unprotected people” (people who are investigated for crimes or people living in places not belonging to them). Last group consists of people who have non-adequate living conditions. The last census was carried out in 2021. The data are not yet available.</p>					<p>for housing; mobile homes). Data on primary homeless – about people living on the street have not been the subject of a census.</p>
25. Slovenia	<p>There is no national count of homeless people in Slovenia. The existing data is the data on the users of services</p>	Country	Annually	-	Ministry of Labour, Family and Social Affairs	-

	for the homeless limited to services that are funded by the Ministry of Labour, Family and Social Affairs. They are majority of all services.					
26. Spain	Homeless census carried out by the National Statistical Office that define homeless people as follows: A homeless person is considered to be one who does not have access during the reference period to accommodation that meets the commonly accepted human habitability criteria, whether the accommodation is	Municipalities with more than 20,000 inhabitants.	Without a fixed periodicity . Previous national surveys in 2005 and 2012. The last in 2022.	Homeless people aged 18 and over who come to centres offering accommodation and/or catering services. Survey on Centres and Services to Support for Homeless Persons.	National Statistical Office	Survey carried out by the National Statistical Office on a sample designed to obtain information at a national level on the group considered to be homeless, both in terms of their number and the socioeconomic characteristics of this population.

	legally their property or if it is rented, or occupied for free with the permission of the owner, or under contract or other arrangement of a non-temporary nature (including those provided by the public sector or non-governmental organizations and those provided by employers). ¹⁸					
27. Sweden	The Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare employs a broad definition of homelessness, ranging across four situations that people may find	Municipality	Six years There have been five national homelessness surveys in Sweden	Gender; age; migrant background; household composition; Types of homelessness:	Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare	Survey sent by the Swedish National Board of Health and Welfare to all municipalities. The data was collected for one week (3-9 april 2017). Questionnaires sent out to organizations that have contact

¹⁸ <https://www.ine.es/en/daco/daco42/epsh/epshper22en.pdf>

	<p>themselves in for various lengths of time.</p> <p>Situation 1 - Acute homelessness</p> <p>Situation 2 - Institution or assisted living</p> <p>Situation 3 - Long-term living arrangements organised by the Social Services</p> <p>Situation 4 - Private short-term living arrangement</p> <p>'Acute homelessness' includes people sleeping in public spaces and those in overnight shelters. It also includes those in accommodation for homeless people, as well as those living in mobile homes, non-</p>		<p>since 1993 (1993, 1999, 2005, 2011 and 2017). The definition has changed every time a survey has been conducted. This has complicated the task of comparing the figures.</p>	<p>Temporarily / 10 years or longer.</p>		<p>with people experiencing homelessness. The social services constitute the largest share of the respondents.</p>
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	<p>conventional buildings and temporary structures (i.e. ETHOS Light categories 1, 2, 3 and 5).</p> <p>‘Institutional or assisted living’ includes people residing in institutions who lack housing prior to release (i.e. ETHOS Light category 4).</p> <p>People in ‘long-term living arrangements’ include those who have been assigned accommodation through the social services. The housing situation is contractual, and often includes supervision and housing support (this</p>					
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	<p>category has no equivalent in the ETHOS Light definition, but sub-definitions in this category show some resemblance to the category 'transitional supported accommodation' in ETHOS Light category 3).</p> <p>Many municipalities do their own homelessness counts every year or every other year, but they also use different definitions from the one adopted by the National Board of Health and Welfare.</p>					
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